

GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT THE HISTORY OF PEDAGOGICAL TRAINING

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Abstract. *The history of pedagogy dates back to ancient times. Pedagogy can be counted from the time when man invented writing. From the time when the first civilizations arose in world history to the present, pedagogy, human education and intellectual development have played a major role in the development of society. Modern pedagogy has gradually developed from the civilizations of ancient China, Rome, Greece, Central Asia and India.*

Keywords: *Education, pedagogy, historical and pedagogical research, societies, principle, pedagogical thought, cultural studies, sociology.*

PEDAGOGIK TA'LIM TARIXI HAQIDA UMUMIY MA'LUMOT.

Annotatsiya. *Pedagogika ta'limi tarixi qadimgi davrlarga borib taqaladi. Pedagogikani inson yozishni ixtiro qilgan paytdan boshlab sanash mumkin. Jahon tarixida ilk sivilizatsiyalar vujudga kelgan davrdan to hozirgi kungacha jamiyat taraqqiyotida pedagogika, inson tarbiyasi, aqliy taraqqiyoti katta rol o'ynadi. Zamonaviy pedagogika asta-sekin qadimgi Xitoy, Rim, Gretsiya, O'rta Osiyo va Hindiston sivilizatsiyalaridan rivojlandi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Ta'lim, pedagogika, tarixiy-pedagogik tadqiqotlar, jamiyatlar, tamoyil, pedagogik fikr, madaniyatshunoslik, sotsiologiya.*

PEDAGOGIKALIQ T'ALIM TARIYXI HAQQINDA ULIWMA MA'GLIWMAT.

Annotatsiya. *Pedagogika tariyxı áyyemgi dáwirlerge barıp taqaladı. Pedagogikani insan jazıwdı oylap tabıw etken waqıttan baslap sanaw múmkin. Jáhán tariyxında dáslepki sivilizatsiyalar payda bolǵan dáwirden tap házirgi kunge shekem jámiyet rawajlanıwında pedagogika, insan tárbiyası, intellektual rawajlanıwı úlken rol oynadı. Zamanagóy pedagogika az-azdan áyyemgi Kitay, Rim, Gretsiya, Orta Aziya hám Indiya sivilizatsiyalarınan rawajlandi.*

Gilt sózler: *T'elim, pedagogika, tariyxıy -pedagogikalıq izertlewler, jámiyetler, princip, pedagogikalıq pikir, mádeniyatti úyreniw, sotsiologiya.*

Introduction

Education and pedagogical science have several thousand years of history. On this path, pedagogy gradually transformed from disparate views, ideas and theoretical positions into a science. The development of educational institutions was a diverse, contradictory and ambiguous process. Studying the history of education and pedagogical teachings is an important condition for the formation of the general and pedagogical culture of a future specialist, since it provides knowledge about the process of development of the theory and practice of education and upbringing and contributes to the formation of a worldview and pedagogical professionalism.

The history of pedagogy and education as an academic discipline has long been an integral part of pedagogical education; it is one of the oldest branches of pedagogical knowledge, which emerged within pedagogy as early as the mid-19th century. The history of pedagogy and education studies the development of the theory and practice of education, upbringing and training in various historical eras, including modern times in the context of its historical development. At the same time, historical and pedagogical research is not limited to a chronological review of past events and a story about great teachers or great pedagogical ideas.

The main task of science is to find out what the role of education was in societies of past eras and why philosophers and teachers created certain theories in a certain period of time. There are various approaches (or methodological foundations) in the history of pedagogy: formational, ideological, cultural, anthropological, sociological, civilizational (socially oriented). In the development of primitive society and man himself, labor activity of people played a huge role.

The manufacture of simple tools led to the gradual improvement of the human hand, served as the basis for the development of his consciousness. Joint labor activity united the members of primitive society, caused the emergence of articulate speech, helped people stand out from the animal world, unite into a society, develop their thinking, and organize social production. At the dawn of human history, a specific feature was group, collective education.

Education originated in an integrative-syncretic form, i.e. simultaneously as physical, mental and moral-emotional maturation. At first, education was not a special function, it accompanied the transfer of life experience. At an early stage of development of the primitive communal system in pre-tribal society, education acquired a more multifaceted and systematic character in the conditions of a tribal community. Later, the family became the main social unit.

These processes changed the tasks of education, which turned from universal, equal, controlled by the community into class-family. In the history of folk pedagogy, one can distinguish special stages associated with the formation of ethnocultural communities, as well as with changes

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in the distribution of educational functions. Within the clan and tribe, the family was the center of folk pedagogy - ideas, traditions, experience.

Specially appointed persons with experience in organized education appeared: elders, clergy. Taking into account cultural traditions and climatic conditions, family and then forest schools became widespread, where hermit gurus taught. In the 6th century BC, three main ideological trends took shape in China, subsequently transformed into philosophical and religious systems: Taoism, Buddhism and Confucianism. Confucianism turned out to be the official ideology of education and upbringing. Education became widespread. The prestige of a knowledgeable person grew, and a cult of education developed. Ancient Eastern civilizations gave humanity the first examples of schools. The education of Spartans pursued the goal of preparing members of a military community. Education and training in Athens were built differently than in Sparta. The ideal of paideia (education) was reduced to a polysemantic concept - a set of virtues.

In Athens, the idea of a comprehensive formation of a personality with a developed intellect and body culture was practically proclaimed. One of the main aspects of education in Ancient Rome was attention to grammar, literature, rhetoric, the grammatical ideal of education prevailed.

Home education played a leading role. In the families of the Roman nobility, home schooling was prevalent with the invitation of Greek teachers. During the heyday of the Roman Empire, the state education system received priority. Elementary education was given in trivial schools. In the Hellenistic era and then within the framework of Roman civilization, a program of seven liberal arts was formed. Advanced schools were grammar schools. Rhetorical schools existed for young people of aristocratic origin. However, the upbringing of children of individual classes differed in content and nature. A departure from religious education was mainly the secular education of feudal knights. The children of secular feudal lords received the so-called knightly education. During this period, a new type of medieval scholarship arose — scholasticism, the purpose of which was to present doctrine in the form of scientific knowledge. In addition to the spread of church (monastic, cathedral) and secular schools (magistrate, guild, guild), the Middle

Ages also preserved such a form of education as apprenticeship. The pace and scale of the formation of the education system were determined by the development characteristics of each country. In Germany, the issue of school was stimulated by the struggle for the unification of nations. In England, school policy underwent changes in accordance with skillful maneuvering during the implementation of the state course. In France, due to high social activity, the school issue turned out to be one of the hot spots of state policy.

Conclusion

An appeal to the history of pedagogy allows us to more fully understand the course and results of the interaction between society, on the one hand, and school and pedagogy, on the other.

A system of knowledge emerges about how pedagogy reproduced communities and civilizations, how acquired cultural values were consolidated in the sphere of education and training. The idea is formed that pedagogy has always been a noticeable (though not the only) driver of cultural and social evolution.

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